

Enhancing Staff Induction Training on Performance of Public Universities in Coastal Region, Kenya

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Abstract—The goal of this research was to investigate how staff induction training impacts the performance of non-teaching employees at Public Universities in the Coastal Region. The selected Universities for this research were the Main Public Universities namely Pwani University, Technical University of Mombasa, and Taita Taveta University. These universities were chosen as focal points due to the absence of prior research in this area and the identification of pertinent issues within the region. The objectives focused on inclusivity of employee understanding of the University's vision and mission, procedures and policies, technical and practical skills, and job requirements and clarity as components in the staff induction were results to better performance. The evaluation employed the theoretical frameworks of Employee Induction theory (TPI), Organizational role theory, and Kirkpatrick Four-level Model. A descriptive research design was adapted, and data collection involved both primary and secondary sources. Stratified sampling was used to capture employee groups from each university, with a total target population of 728 non-teaching staff members. However, 124 respondents were ultimately included in the study. Data collection methods included structured questionnaires and interviews, with qualitative data analysed thematically and quantitative data assessed using descriptive statistical methods in SPSS version 28. The method of probability used were stratified sampling to ensure comparability and precision. Data collection involved structured questionnaires and interviews, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of participants' perspectives. Pre-testing and refinement of data collection instruments ensured validity and reliability, with a content validity index of 0.894 and a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.9, respectively. The qualitative data was subjected to thematic analysis in order to identify significant themes, and the quantitative data was assessed using descriptive statistical methods in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. The findings revealed significant response rate from both questionnaire recipients (84.9%) and interviewees (50%), highlighting the relevance of the study's objectives. Analysis of demographic data uncovered insights into staff demographics, tenure, and job perceptions, emphasizing the importance of effective induction programs in promoting job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The results identified aspects of staff induction that significantly boost university performance. It shows how effectively communicating the university's vision and mission, streamlining policies and procedures, enhancing induction training, ensuring clarity in job descriptions fostering a supportive environment, providing necessary tools and equipment, and improving policy training and implementation. Challenges

identified included gaps in policy comprehension, ineffective communication of university goals, and inadequate training on workplace systems and procedures. Recommendations focus on enhancing induction programs to integrate organizational vision, clarify roles and responsibilities, and provide practical skills for job performance. Recommendations focus on enhancing induction programs to integrate organizational vision, clarify roles and responsibilities, and provide practical skills for job performance within Public Universities in the Coastal Region of Kenya and beyond.

Index Terms— staff induction, employee work performance, non-teaching staff, new staff, deployed staff, promoted staff.

1. Introduction

Universities globally face the challenge of employee turnover, with skilled individuals leaving and being replaced year after year. The growth in non-teaching staff numbers has been attributed to complex activities and bureaucratic procedures in managing administrative positions. Kwiek, M. (2018) The Kenyan Government's decision to increase University capacity and funding aimed to accommodate more students but also led to the employment of additional staff with diverse skills to enhance operational efficiency Baltaru, R. D., & Soysal, Y. N. (2018).

Non-teaching staff in the Universities, encounter challenges such as poor service, delays in service delivery, and corruption. Researchers have identified factors contributing to employee underperformance, which include slow recruitment, inadequate training, insufficient rewards, and external management interference. The performance of public sector employees significantly impacts the Government, affecting overall productivity and financial stability Avenali, A., Daraio, C., & Wolszczak-Derlacz, J. (2023). Employee turnover within probation period or within five years of joining the University has become common. The dilemma for universities lies in deciding whether to invest in training or not. It worth to note that any neglect in training results in negative consequences, providing induction training therefore enables staff to quickly master their roles, retaining talented personnel as valuable assets. Staff induction training is a crucial process that help

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employees identify their abilities and skills, fostering confidence and recognition.

Recognizing the importance of induction training has become essential for organizations and Universities to compete in attracting and retaining talent. Creating a positive environment for new employees through support and a familiarization of processes is crucial for their successful adjustment to the workplace. Induction training also plays a key role in maintaining organizational culture, ensuring consistency in procedures, and serving as a reminder of previously learned concepts. The quality and relevance of content, trainer skills, experiences, and organizational expectations determine the effectiveness of induction training. Avenali, A., Daraio, C., & Wolszczak-Derlacz, J. (2023). Training should not merely be done but training ought to empower employees to be the driving force in achievement of goals in order for the University to retain the name of centre of excellence by having excellence in employee performance Orlick T. (2015).

It is a great concern that organizations still regard induction as a waste of resources. The training is done as a matter of fulfilling the laid down procedures as required by law in conformity to set criteria for employee training. This has continued even in the 21st century induction training is being done with a lot of inconsistent and substandard content as stated by Beyers, L.J.E., and Nkoana, P.M.W. (2016). This has been attributed to a lack of awareness and limited finances to provide good training as cited by Akech J. (2016). The character of the employees has been considered to influence on the outcome of the training Maruhi, L. W. (2018) and skills and knowledge not communicated well making the employees encounter difficulty on delivering assignments thus causing anxiety, emotional, stress and high cases of resignation as stated by P. Akiror (2018).

The organizations that have neglected induction training have been left with high costs of recruiting new employees, and delays in transition due to slow learning to fit in the system and be able deliver. Eventually, most of the employees look for other better places to work as cited by Viljane (2018). Nevertheless, effective induction training has resulted in the smooth transition of employees in their new environments and have adapted to their respective work resulting in good performance within a short time as cited by Shayo F. (2020).

In addition, the training has made employee's confident and committed due to better understanding of their tasks and knowledge on procedures and policies attaining compliance in their processes and good performance as stated by E. D. Leiti (2015). Similarly, it enables Universities to obtain competitive advantage, job satisfaction and fulfilment of their employees. The sense of belonging developed as result of understanding the University vision and the employees are able to acquire knowledge to develop quality programs and policies of better and quality services available to all as stated Khakayi, S. W. (2017).

The theory of Theoretical, Practical and Integration (TPI) has been widely used successfully by many scholars and reveals that as part of learning for new employees. They need to interact with the existing employees for smooth and conducive

environment for settling down. Using this theory the employees' performance will be depended on the knowledge gained through the theoretical and practical skills. When employees get to know the vital processes of the universities, they are able to be effective at work within a short time as they are able to interact and work as a team as stated by Kumar (2021). When the new employees get to know the organization's driving tools it becomes an opportunity to understand the mission, vision, and values. Role theory has been used and achieved to explain the gap between supervisors and employees. The use of role theory helps employees to understand the roles with more clarity as noted by J., Li, X., Wang, B., Song, B., Zhang, W., Chen, M., & Qu, Y. (2018).

2. Statement of the Problem

Universities in China experienced significant growth in student enrolment as stated in CUE report (2018). However, the efforts to increase student numbers in Kenyan Public Universities have led to challenges, primarily centred around inadequate funding. Despite the Government's increased budgetary allocation of 56% in the academic year of 2023/2024, a substantial portion of the funds has been directed toward employee salaries, leaving limited resources for the university development.

The projection of 2023/2024 released in February 2024 reflected a deficit of 27, 921,094,00 of the approved allocation as indicated in the Education report (2023). Therefore, Universities need governance with high visibility to balance their priorities and survive the stiff competition from the Private Universities. Therefore, the management of the university in terms of finance is crucial as it not management well as result in low production graduates who cannot meet the national and international standards as outlined in the Kenya's Vision 2030.

The Government's responsibility, as mandated by the constitution and Executive Orders of 2020, is to manage Public Universities and provide a policy framework for their operations. Therefore, the Ministry of Education have a responsibility to monitor time to time that the education of the Universities in order to remain relevant and manage good quality. To accomplish this mandate there is a need to have quality staff both teaching and non-teaching. The employees being an asset to discharge this important responsibility, it is the duty of Human Resource Management of every University to conduct proper staff induction to meet the University expectations Miriam W.W. (2023).

The Kenya Universities are being faced by inadequate funding amidst other challenges like appointment of administration who lack capacity, skills and passion for the sustenance of the university. Harmonization of the terms of services for both teaching and non-teaching is still not completed which has hampered the performance of the university staff instead of pulling together they pull apart. When it comes to population almost all the university have the highest population of non-teaching staff compared to teaching staff to the ratio of about 3:1 and has caused a burden and role conflicts and this was reiterated recently by the Cabinet Minister of Education on 8th November 2023 that Government was

freezing the employment of non-teaching of lower cadre in Public University and only teaching staff would be employed.

Subsequently majority of the non-teaching staff has been noted with lack understanding of their role in contributing to the University's success. There is a noticeable gap between academia's perception and prioritization of non-teaching staff as stated in Training Education report (2021). In 2021, the Vice Chancellor of the University of Nairobi said Universities should prioritize nurturing skills and strengths not only for student but also staff so that good performance is to be realized. Universities are places of academia, but without the hard work and dedication of non-academic staff, the University cannot run efficiently and effectively Amy Jenkins (2023).

The main problem revolves around the financial constraints, governance issues, and ineffective human resource management in the Public Universities in Kenya, with a focus on the Coastal Region Public Universities. Public Universities in Kenya are still below in their performance and researchers have cited several factors including ineffective staff induction, political and ethnic pressures influencing administrative appointments, lack of harmonization in the terms of service for teaching and non-teaching staff. Different countries are facing

different challenges in conducting staff induction. Several researchers have concurred that the induction content needs reviewing though the factors are not the same some in terms of how the training mode should be presented, some the content should include challenges observed during the training and how the induction is communicated, understood and applied. Universities need high-visibility governance to address these challenges and remain competitive with Private Universities.

The disconnect between academia and non-teaching staff, as well as the inadequacies in communication during induction training, contribute to poor employee performance and a fragile attachment to University goals and therefore there is need to bridge this gap. Despite many studies that have been done it is still clear that there are still gaps to be filled. Staff induction training is crucial so that universities can fulfil their mandate and continue creating opportunities which impart knowledge to transform the communities and the Society of Kenya in general as reiterated by Jonyo (2018).

A. Objectives of the Study

To evaluate influence of understanding Vision and Mission on performance of non-teaching Employees of Public Universities in Coastal Region, Kenya, to examine influence of awareness and adherence to procedures on performance of non-teaching Employees of Public Universities in Coastal Region, Kenya, to assess the acquisition of technical and practical on performance of non-teaching Employees of Public Universities in Coastal Region, Kenya, and to establish influence of job requirements and role clarity on the performance of non-teaching employees of Public Universities in Coastal Region, Kenya.

3. Literature Review

A. Understanding Vision and Mission on Performance of Non-Teaching Staff

We are in times where employees do not look for employment alone but to get employment where the vision and mission aligned to their individual objectives. According to the research, 52% of UK employees are unaware of their organization's mission and has affected the employee direction to focus Pritchard, M., & Elaine, E. (2020). The mission of the organization is the reason for their existence and the vision is what they want to achieve. Therefore, organizations cannot thrive without a vision and goal; it is like embarking on a journey without knowing where you are going. As a result, it is critical to communicate with all New, Deployed, and Promoted (NDP) employees about the organization's vision and mission Jonyo, B., & Ouma, C. (2018).

Learning vision and mission during induction assist employees to focus on their tasks and fulfil the bigger mission. It makes them feel the sense of purpose and this act as a motivator to work effectively. Having knowledge of the vision and mission it enables the staff to contribute to decision making faster at all levels without compromising the goals of the University. It makes the employees to be accountable of all their duties and responsibilities as mentioned by J. Hetland, H. Hetland, A. B. Bakker, and E. Demerouti (2018).

Communicating mission and vision, enables the Universities to ensure activities are in alignment with the University goals. The knowledge of vision empowers employees to have good foresight of the future and become better placed to contribute in the achievement of long-term goals which include better communication, trust, collaboration, team spirit to achieve the overall University performance Ahmed (2019). Subsequently the employees trust will be build knit relationship which are able to accomplish and exceed expectation M. Mustafa, F. K. Alzubi, and A. Bashayreh (2021).

B. Understanding Policies and Procedures on Performance of Non-Teaching Employees

According to the survey done by Guide Spark stated that only about 30% of the employees do not read handbooks and therefore it is of concern for employers how the employees can get to know about the procedures and policies of the organization. Policies are guidelines on how processes are done, while procedures are instructions on how the job requirements of one employee are separate from one another. Procedures are designed to ensure that service delivery is consistent and of the right quality and consistent processes contribute to an organization's positive reputation

They are vital in the organization for processes to be done consistently and employers should ensure therefore policies and procedures are up to date to facilitate work completion and to explain why it is done the way it is done to help in resolving issues before they emerge Chillakuri, B. (2020). Doing assigned work without knowledge of policies can result in errors, rework and inefficiencies impacting negative performance. It is important for the policies to be communicated and trained so that employees can obtain key information on how to apply the

policies to the betterment of their performance at work.

Although Gasior, M. (2017) argued that about 69% of executives are not sure how current policies can address the organization's needs. The effectiveness of policies rests on how well they are organized, communicated and trained, if not trained and communicated properly it does not address the needs. Policy Management Report (2020). The employees should be trained on application of the policies and procedures and not just given to keep in the office. The sizes of some policies are large making the employees lack the motivation of reading.

C. Learning Through Technical and Practical Skills on Performance of Non-Teaching

When the employees learn skills they become specialized to perform their duties and benefit the organization. Skills make the employee become more competent and confident to perform. The employees who are knowledgeable will be vital to train the new employees to integrate into the workplace and be able to accomplish task with minimal distraction. During interaction with other colleagues the new employees with gain skills through observing the experienced employees on skills to operate equipment and tools. The technical knowledge to access systems for essential information and skills to handle office documents and clients management are all beneficial to the new staff to understand as noted by Kay Rose (2021).

According to Lorman's blog on training statistics of 2022 seventy-six (76) per cent of employees shows that if the organization can train them on additional skills they can be loyal to the organization and perform well. Employees who acquire the necessary skills can be productive B. Ozkeser (2019). Not only are the technical skills necessary in today's work environment, but practical skills remain crucial assets and employers do prefer employees with practical skills rather than merely those who can read and write.

Consequently, the more an employee knows how to accomplish a task with minimal time makes the organization succeed even if it's not specifically mentioned in the job description the more valuable the employee will be to an employer McGunagle, D., & Zizka, L. (2020). The skills should be specialized for the employee workstation so that the obtained knowledge and skills benefit the organization Kumar (2021).

D. Understanding of Job Requirements and Role Clarity on The Performance of Non-Teaching Employees

Job clarity is particularly crucial in service-based organizations where employees need to understand their tasks and responsibilities to provide effective services. When role expectations are unclear, workers are hesitant and lack initiative Samie F, Riahi L, Tabibi S. J. (2015). Job requirements are listed in the job description of every employee and the new employees need to know how each assigned duty in the description is done. When there are changes in the structures, duties can impact job clarity and should be managed appropriately. Failure of Universities to recognize that different departments have different processes, the changing of duties when the organization undergoes reorganization, or people are

promoted or deployed makes job clarity of great concern. Regrettably, new jobs are rarely defined and explained to the employees. When roles are specified, the organization can find the proper individuals for the job, and therefore the employees will work effectively and increase efficiency at work M. Mahmood, A. Ostrovskiy, and N. Capar (2022).

Organizations should focus on more than just creating job descriptions they should actively manage the implementation of employees' duties. Every organization's primary plan should be to redefine their employees' duties and expectations and manage their implementation rather than simply writing job descriptions that appear on their employees' files only as paper. Some organizations do not value job definitions, and so employees who are given assignments not specified in their job descriptions resulting in frustration rather than motivation, satisfaction and performance.

4. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework outlines the interconnections between key components, showing how the vision, roles, policies, and skills contribute to shaping staff induction, which, in turn, influences employee performance, with the institutional matrix playing a pivotal role in this relationship definition of roles, responsibilities, determine the communication channels which are vital during induction training. The decisions and resource allocation are determined by the organizational structure. In summary the institutional matrix which help to shape how induction practices will be done. This framework provides a structured approach to understanding the dynamics and variables at play in the context of staff induction and its influence on the performance of employees.

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework
Source: Researcher 2024

5. Theoretical Framework

A. Employee Induction Theory

This theory was adapted as it will guide to investigate how

understanding the vision, familiarly with procedures, acquisition of skills and job clarity will influence the non-teaching staff work performance.

B. Organization Role Theory

This theory is a valuable tool for clarifying expectations and navigating any disputes that may develop during staff induction, contributing to enhanced work clarity, role understanding, and eventual improvement of the employee performance.

C. Kirkpatrick Four level Model

This model is useful because as a guide to the implementation of induction training to employee performance. The reaction of staff on the training and intake on the training content is learning and after the training the knowledge and skills gained will enable them to renew their mindset and change to obtain results.

D. Methodology

The quantitative data and qualitative data collection methods were used. For quantitative data a structured questionnaire were administered and for qualitative data interviews guides were used. The pilot testing was done before the actual data collection and validity and reliability of instruments were tested. Validity the study researcher adapted CVI and for reliability Cronbach's Alpha formula were used and both tests were above 0.8 and 0.9 respectively.

E. Research Design

The researcher utilized descriptive research design to outline how staff induction training affected performance at the Public Universities in the Coastal Region. The descriptive research design was adopted because of its significant advantage of not influencing participants' behaviour. Random sampling and stratified sampling were used to collect data and instruments for testing analysed using SPSS 28 for quantitative analysis and thematic analysis for qualitative analysis.

F. Location of the Study

Pwani University, Taita Taveta University, and the Technical

University of Mombasa are the Public Universities in the coastal region where this research was conducted. This area of research had not been done in the three Universities and the research problem had been identified in the region that is why it was chosen at the best location.

6. Discussions and Results

A. Questionnaire Response

Table 1
Sample size

Name of the University	Sampled	Answered	Percentage
Pwani University	44	41	93.2
Technical University of Mombasa	68	51	75.0
Taita Taveta University	36	31	86.1
Total	146	124	84.9

From table 1, it shows that 146 questionnaires were given to the non-teaching respondents, 124 (84.9%) were responded to successfully; 41 from Pwani university, 51 from technical university of Mombasa and 31 from Taita Taveta University. According to Pandey and Pandey (2021), a response rate of 50% is deemed acceptable, while a rate of 70% or higher is regarded as good. Therefore, the study's return rate of 84.9% was good.

From the findings on the table 2, a large number 51 (40.1%) of the non-teaching respondents were of age bracket between 35 – 44 years. Majority 67 (54%) were male while 85 (68.5%) had served the universities for 10 years or more. Most 55 (44.3%) of the respondents were of job group middle level and 120 (96.8%) were employed on permanent terms of service. Large population are permanent means they have job security of their work. The respondents from all universities selected respondents those who were experienced enough to understand the effect of staff induction training on performance of Public Universities non-teaching employees in coastal region, Kenya.

7. Discuss and Interpretation

A. Comprehension of Vision and Mission

The study found that while non-teaching staff recognize the

Table 2
Bio data of the respondents

Bio data	Frequency	Percentage	
Age of respondents	18-24	2	1.6
	25-34	13	10.5
	35-44	51	40.1
	45-54	43	34.7
	55 and above	15	12.1
Gender of respondents	Male	67	54.0
	Female	57	46.0
Number of years having served in the current University	Less than 1 year	4	3.2
	1-3 years	6	4.8
	4-6 years	10	8.1
	7-9 years	19	15.3
	10 years or more	85	68.5
Job level of respondents	Senior level	18	14.5
	Middle level	55	44.3
	Junior level	29	23.4
	Support staff	22	17.7
Terms of service of respondents	Permanent	120	96.8
	Contract	4	3.2
Total	124	100	

importance of the university's vision and mission, there are significant challenges in how these principles are communicated. Inconsistent communication methods have led to varied levels of understanding among staff, impacting their performance. A structured approach to communicating the vision and mission during induction is essential for staff alignment and organizational success.

The figure 2, shows that the majority of the respondents said the vision was a guide to the University in achieve their mission. This is below expectation and its shows that significant portion of stakeholders felt that the Universities did not run to the letter of what is laid down to in their vision. A large population of 33 percent of the respondents seemed to have a disconnect between the activities being operated by the Universities and its vision as stated in the vision statement. The integration of the university's vision, mission, and institutional culture into daily activities and staff understanding is lacking. This gap undermines clarity of direction and staff alignment with core objectives.

Fig. 2.

B. Awareness and Adherence to Policies and Procedures

Fig. 3. Ratings of improved performance as a result of familiarity with procedures and policies in line with employee roles

1	Administrative Policies/procedures	30%
2	Safety/Security Policies/procedures	10%
3	Human Resource Policies and Manual& procedures Code of conduct and ethics policy/procedures Staff training and development policies/procedure	37%
4	Communication policy/Records Policy/procedures	3%
5	Finance Policies/procedures	20%

Findings indicate that a notable minority of non-teaching staff, particularly those in junior and support roles, lack awareness of university policies and procedures. This gap is attributed to ineffective communication channels and insufficient training. The complexity and volume of policies further exacerbate this issue, leading to potential violations and misunderstandings. There is a need for streamlined, accessible policy communication and regular updates to ensure all staff are informed and compliant.

C. University Policies and Procedures

From figure 3, on familiarity of core policies and procedures is shows that staff are not aware of the policies that exist to at least 50 percent. The highest percentage is 37 and the lowest is 5 percent though the university is the formulation centre of policies. That fact that 37% of the staff perceive their familiarity with procedures and policies as average indicates the significant portion of the workforce may not have a comprehensive understanding of the policies and procedures which could potentially lead to inconsistencies in behaviours and performance across the departments which can impact the efficiency, decision making and university effectiveness to its mandate.

D. Acquisition of Technical Knowledge and Practical Skills

The existing induction programs were found lacking in equipping new staff with necessary technical skills and knowledge to operate workplace equipment and systems. This deficiency leads to errors, slow performance, and equipment failures. Additionally, inadequate training on document handling and customer interaction was highlighted, with staff often learning these skills through observation rather than formal instruction. Comprehensive technical training should be integrated into the induction program to address these gaps.

Table 3

Induction to skills at the workstation enabled the good operation of the system, access information, and use other equipment within the assigned section

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	25	20.1
Disagree	50	40.3
Neutral	29	23.3
Agree	14	11.2
Strongly agree	6	4.8
Total	124	100.0

The table 3, on induction to skills at the work station to operate systems to access information and use of equipment indicated that 20.1% of the respondents strongly disagree, 40.3% disagree, 23.3% neutral, 11.2% agree, 4.8% strongly agree. From the findings it shows 60.4% have negative perceptions towards induction to skills and knowledge at the workstation in regard to operating systems, access to

information and use of office equipment. If the induction training to skills and knowledge at the workstation is insufficient in preparing staff for their assignments it can lead to frustration, low performance.

The workplace systems need technical knowledge to operate therefore staff should be trained on using effectively the system to avoid inefficiencies and errors which lowers the performance. In cases where there is no necessary equipment for employees to perform their tasks efficiently it is upon the university to purchase the equipment and any communication that need to be communicated on access to information should be communicated so that staff might be assisted adequately to prevent delays which can lead to confusion and frustration among employees.

E. Comprehension of Job Requirements and Clarity of Roles

The study revealed inconsistencies in communicating job descriptions and performance expectations to new staff, resulting in confusion and inefficiency. Clear communication of job roles and expectations is crucial for staff motivation, satisfaction, and performance. Regular feedback mechanisms and interaction with experienced colleagues can facilitate better understanding and integration of new employees into their roles.

Table 4

Extent to which lack of clarity contribute to delays and lower employee performance

Rating	Frequency	Percentage
Little delay	26	21.0
Highest delay	55	44.4
None	7	5.6
Very little delay	7	5.6
More delay	28	22.6
Total	124	100.0

A large number 55 (44.4%) rated the extent to which lack of clarity at work contribute to delays and lower employee performance to have the highest delay as shown in table 4. Lack of clarity can cause a great impact in the university processes as it can lead to inefficiencies in the operations and need for clarifications in the roles and responsibilities therefore causing delays. To the university a lot of missed deadlines to assignment can disrupt the calendar and university progress. The universities all strive to maintain the reputation and lack of clarity and gradually affect the reputation of the university. According to 2023 statistics, timing is crucial in staff induction to prevent disengagement. According to Combs and Woehr (2017), it has also aided in helping staff members discover their own potential and expectations, as well as the best ways for them to contribute. These are critical components of induction that support employee success and retention. Universities should prioritize clear communication and documentation of processes. This may involve creating detailed process manuals, providing training and support to staff and students, and regularly reviewing and updating procedures to ensure they remain relevant and effective. Additionally, seeking feedback from stakeholders can help identify areas where processes may be unclear and in need of improvement. By investing in clarity

and efficiency, universities can enhance their effectiveness, reputation, and overall success.

8. Conclusion

The research aimed to explore the impact of staff induction training on the performance of non-teaching employees at Public Universities in the Coastal Region. By focusing on Pwani University, Technical University of Mombasa, and Taita Taveta University, it addressed a gap in prior research within the region. The objectives emphasized the importance of employee understanding regarding university communication of vision and mission, application of policies and procedures, technical knowledge, practical skills, and job requirements and job clarity.

On the vision and mission and its effects on the staff work performance showed that a significant impact of understanding the university's vision and mission on employee performance, with those who recognize its importance performing 76.5% better than those who do not. However, the perception of staff varies, and many employees felt that the current communication methods were not adequate. Only a small proportion of respondents believed that the university vision and mission had been aligned with their daily tasks, and a notable percentage indicated that poor communication contributes to substandard staff performance at the University. The university can embrace implementation of structured and comprehensive approach on how to communicate its vision and mission. All the new staff from the start of employees should understand the mandate of the university, objectives and values to more on one direction with others. The standardization of the channels to provide this information were essential to avoid miscommunication of information. The university aim should be for all staff to understand how their individual roles incline to the university vision and mission so that all can experience sense of purpose, staff motivation and overall performance to the university.

The findings on the awareness and adherence to the university procedures and policies by non-teaching revealed that familiarity of the university procedure at least 50 percent of the staff are not aware of the policies formulated though the university is the formulation centre of policies. An estimate of 37% of the staff perceive their familiarity with procedures and policies as average indicates the significant portion of the workforce may not have a comprehensive understanding of the policies and procedures which could potentially lead to inconsistencies in behaviours and performance across the departments leading to inefficiency in the decision making and university effectiveness to its mandate. It was also established that the majority (40.3) percent of the respondents got to know about the policies at their work station. It must be understood that policies to be communicated and trained so that they employees can be able to apply it at on their operations causing better changes in the performance. This also has been supported by Gasior, M. (2017) who argued that about 69% of executives were not sure how their policies addressed their needs. The effectiveness of policies rests on how well they are organized, communicated and trained, if not trained and communicated properly it does not address the needs. Policy Management

Report (2020).

The policies to guide the process should be updated to the current reviews to accommodate times and technology, employees should be aware of the policies which guide the process comprehensively, and the necessary clauses should be clear enough to guide. Failure of any of this means failure to deliver quality processes of the university and other assumptions that because policies exist should direct the processes effective is not true as supported by Chillakuri (2020) that for the policies to direct to completion the processes assigned its needs to be upto date. According to the findings it was shown that indeed familiarity of policies and procedures change staff to have positive change in their job performance which confirm that if all the staff are able to familiar with the procedures and policies then there will be overall performance. Therefore, the university should strive to strategize a better communication plan on how to keep all staff informed about policy updates and revisions. Nevertheless, training on procedures and policies with having staff be able to access them is exercise in futility. As per the findings on this study showed that 47 percent could not access the policies. Universities formulate numerous policies but there has been slow in training employees to get knowledge and understanding of the existing policies as stated by Mchete (2020) on role of induction that university was not doing enough to train staff on the relevant policies.

Acquisition of skills and technical knowledge is crucial on work performance of non-teaching staff. The study revealed that the existing induction program did not cover skills the new staff need to obtain at the work station in order to operate systems, access information and use of different equipment therefore the new staff training is insufficient in preparing staff for their assignments leading to frustration, low performance. The workplace systems need technical knowledge to operate therefore staff should be trained on using effectively the system to avoid inefficiencies and errors which lowers the performance. It was also depicted that communication was not sufficient to enable the new staff transit smoothly in regard to accessing essential information. Its addition the study showed that 64.5% believe that skills and knowledge to handle documents was not adequately addressed during the induction at the workstation. Addition skills before assignment more responsibilities revealed that 32 percent were trained to their new roles while the rest were not trained. The deployed and promoted staff change of responsibilities is affected by this factor and is a potential gap which the university should plan for and consider as part of induction training for staff whose tasks needs different skills to operate and be competent to deliver their assignments. The induction done by existing staff at the workstation has significant portion of impact training the new staff obtained compared to other personnel mandated with the process. This paints a picture that the existing induction program is not effective in preparing staff to perform technical tasks, handling documents and clients still is inadequate.

This study revealed inconsistency in communication of job descriptions which posed a risk of inefficiency at work and confusion at the workplace. Significant portion of the

respondents showed that the job description was just on paper and not been explained to or adhered to as required. The study showed that other staff could not access essential information and resources to perform well due to lack of proper orientation with their colleagues which could have assisted them to operate the systems and processes at the university. The study results indicate a lack of consistency and clarity in communication within the organization regarding changes and updates to job expectations and requirements. The fact that a significant portion of respondents feel they are not adequately communicated to suggests a potential gap in the communication process especially for those staff who get promoted or transferred.

Concerning the job clarity about half indicated that the job descriptions provided clarity to work operations while the other half indicated that the job descriptions were not sufficient and might cause a potential confusion and inefficiency. It was also noted that a significant portion said their roles were not clear this indicated that many staff did not have well defined roles leading to uncertainty and conflicts. The lack of clarity impacts the university processes and its reputation and therefore job descriptions when explained can boost the overall performance at the university.

9. Recommendations

Universities are centres of excellence and therefore there is need to have staff who are efficient and effective. Therefore, staff induction training remains very crucial to attain this performance and excellence. The study revealed that the vision and mission information did not have a standardized way of being communicated to the staff and cause disintegration of essential requirements of the university. Consequently, having more interactive sessions during induction training and aligning of the vision to their daily duties will speak volumes in their minds instead of just words on the walls. The staff induction training is considered the first training for the new staff therefore knowing and understanding the vision of the institution they are joining is crucial for the present and the future expectations. The study also revealed lack of familiarity policies which are crucial especially for the universities who are in the forefront of formulating numerous policies. Formulation and keeping polices in the custody are not enough staff need to be trained on applicability of the essential policies especially at the induction period so that when they start to handle their responsibilities, they are able to be in compliance with the requirements. It also helps to minimize making administrative errors and wrong decisions which can high cost for the university. Compliance and reputation go hand and hand given that universities also faced stiff competition from private universities and when there is no compliance and present of inconsistencies of processes it can make the universities reputation tarnish. In addition, creation of room for the new staff to seek clarification and make suggestions in regards to job descriptions not well explained, policies clauses not clear, need and provide feedback on processes can help avoid delays later when they are given assignments. Inclusion on essential skills to assist them settle faster at the workstation should be provided

formally. Many universities just rely on the existing staff to teach the new staff without making it official who is particular has been assigned the work to ensure the new staff is inducted to accessing system, handling documents, clients and other requirements and standards to be adhered to and maintenance of feedback from the new staff after induction further improvement.

A. Future Research

Investigate the role of organizational culture and leadership in shaping the effectiveness of staff induction programs could provide valuable insights for enhancing induction practices in public universities.

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